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The Main Key Features of Self Study in Improving the Process of Learning Foreign Languages

Qo'ziyeva Ruhshona,
Student

Abstract: *Nowadays it is necessary to properly organize and introduce the foreign language teaching process in higher educational institutions. Knowing how to organize it correctly will help all the teachers and learners to solve the goal and task. This article focuses on the role of self-study on language learning process. In recent years, foreign language learning process has been changing from teacher-based to self-study-based environments. Relying on language learning theories, methods, experiences, research findings, learners and educators developed language learning strategies.*

Key words: *foreign language learning, native language, non-native language, teacher-centred environment, student-centred environment, self-study, exposure, imitate, native-like proficiency, productive language skills, receptive language skills..*

In today's modern world, many people are learning external languages since being someone who is bilingual or multilingual, meaning that being able to use at least two or three languages can really help them to use open, golden opportunities related to studying in abroad, traveling to the different countries and well-paid job opportunities. As long as many people have been informed about benefits of learning and knowing other languages, it has been clear that the number of foreign language enthusiasts is gradually increasing. And most of the cases, doing self-study has been preferred by the large amount of learners because of several reasons. The most important one is that it is the age of speedy. As a result of technological advancements and increasing tendencies of the available resources all around the globe, conventional way of teaching and learning new languages, meaning that teacher-centred environments has been changing student-centred, self-study environments. According to the latest research on the number of internet users over the globe in March 1st 2024, around 66% population of the world have access to the internet. There are nearly 8 billion people on the Earth and 5.35 billion out of them use internet. And this means a lot. With the help of using internet, people have opportunities for learning everything, including foreign languages on their own by being in their comfort zones. Therefore most of the people who enthusiastic about new languages prefer self-study.

Because they know that the process of learning a new language is a natural process which can be achieved by exposure and practical ways rather than only learning theory based grammatical rules. Self-study also named as self-directed learning or auto-didacticism and at the same time it is a deep and challenging process since it requires a strong desire, the highest level of self-esteem, a feeling of responsibility from learners. In order to achieve success in this procedure, learners should be familiarized with the several necessary things which can contribute to the positive result. Here is the list of those 8 main contributors of satisfying outcomes:

1. Setting clear goals. It should be set up clear goals. Learners should know clearly that how much time they are going to spend for this process and what level they are going to achieve. It should be crystal clear that whether they are going to take a language testing exam after self-study or they just need basic conversation in that language, maybe become a fluent.

2. Creating a study schedule. They should arrange a study schedule like allocating exact time and location where is quite and comfortable place that you can focus on language learning process without any kind of distractions on a daily basis for that language since consistency is the only vital factor in positive result and making growing progress. In another words, exposure, meaning that creating an atmosphere which that language can be used and immersing to this environment.

As an simple example, all of us know our mother tongue from our childhood without learning any new words and grammatical rules and we could speak even when we were really young because of the environment, our parents spoke us and we responded although we were unfamiliar with the rules of that language. We just imitated them how to behave and how to speak, express our feelings and opinions. We did it, we could speak because of the atmosphere. Now, all you need to know is that you should create an environment like that you can practice the language rather than learning only theory.

3. Being able to differentiate and use variety sources. They should be able to differentiate beneficial reachable resources with unnecessary sources. They should use different materials such as textbooks, online language learning apps, podcasts and videos in order to make the process more engaging and improve their receptive language skills.

4. Practicing regularly. As long as language learning is a skill which requires real life practice. It is clear that by the more practice and the more use the language in the real life applications that has been learned currently can give the more satisfying result.

5. Keeping a language learning journal. It can be a life long friend for learners. They can write down the new things that they learned in terms of vocabularies, phrases, grammar rules, structures and they revise them whenever and wherever they want.

6. Finding a partner who can help and give feedback in this procedure. Maybe friends from other countries by social media platforms and practicing productive language skills with them in the interesting ways.

7. Using various test materials to identify whether it is been achieving progress or not and rooms for improvement.

8. Staying motivated. In order to keep the motivation in this milestone, it should be celebrated even every single victories related to being able to remember new words, structures and others.

1. Websites:

- Duolingo (<https://www.duolingo.com/>): Offers interactive lessons and exercises to help improve English language skills.

- BBC Learning English (<http://www.bbc.co.uk/learningenglish>): Provides a wide range of resources, including videos, articles, and quizzes for learners of English.
- EnglishClub (<https://www.englishclub.com/>): Offers grammar lessons, vocabulary exercises, and resources for learners at all levels.
- ESL Gold (<https://www.eslgold.com/>): Features grammar lessons, vocabulary activities, and listening exercises for English language learners.

2. YouTube Channels:

- Learn English with Misterduncan (<https://www.youtube.com/user/duncaninchina>): Provides engaging lessons on English grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation.
- Rachel's English (<https://www.youtube.com/user/rachelsenglish>): Focuses on American English pronunciation and accent reduction.
- BBC Learning English (<https://www.youtube.com/user/bbclearningenglish>): Offers a variety of videos on grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation for English learners.
- EngVid (<https://www.youtube.com/user/engvid>): Provides lessons on a wide range of English language topics, including grammar, vocabulary, and idioms. (These websites and YouTube channels offer valuable resources for self-study in English and can help learners improve their language skills at their own pace.)

References:

1. No. 610 dated 11.08.2017. On measures to further improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions <https://lex.uz/docs/-3304915?ONDATE=13.05.2019>
2. Foreign language learning and teaching. Aleidine J. Moeller and Theresa Catalano 2015 . University of Nebraska, Lincoln
3. Internet Usage Statistics In 2024 – Forbes Home <https://www.forbes.com/home-improvement/internet/internet-statistics/#:~:text=There%20are%205.35%20billion%20internet%20users%20worldwide.&text=Out%20of%20the%20nearly%208,the%20internet%20according%20to%20Statista>
4. The Effectiveness of Self-studying Strategies in Language Learning. Sükrü Yigit Salihoglu, Turkey. December 2020 .
5. <https://www.hlomag.co.uk/dec20/effectiveness-of-self-studying-strategies#:~:text=Language%20learning%20is%20a%20unique,in%20the%20faith%20of%20students>
6. <https://www.hlomag.co.uk/dec20/effectiveness-of-self-studying-strategies#:~:text=Language%20learning%20is%20a%20unique,in%20the%20faith%20of%20students>.
7. Strategies To Learn A Language At Home <https://www.babbel.com/en/magazine/7-ways-to-learn-a-language-without-a-teacher#:~:text=Learn%20The%20Language%20As%20It's%20Really%20Spoken&text=Reading%20the%20words%20of%20a,and%20practicing%20the%20sounds%20yourself>.